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Contents

Summary & Objective	4
Methodology.....	5
The overall vision	5
Lessons learned from previous DSTs implementation	6
Action plans.....	6
Short-term deployment.....	7
a. Toward widespread implementation of available oncDST	7
b. Integrate Patient-Centred consultations	8
c. OncDSTs enhancement.....	8
Mid-term deployment.....	9
d. Supporting MTB deployment through widespread MTB module adoption and implementation	9
e. Impact assessment of EU-oncDST implementation	10
f. Streamlining regulations, guidelines, and reimbursement frameworks.....	11
Long-term deployment.....	11
g. Harmonized short- and mid-term activities	11
h. Leverage the data-driven precision oncology module	11
i. Digital Twin exploration to support MTB recommendations.....	12
Deployment opportunities.....	12
Conclusion.....	14
Bibliography	15
Annexe.....	19

Summary & Objective

Clinical decision-making has become increasingly complex, and oncology decision support tools (oncDSTs) play a pivotal role in alleviating the cognitive burden on clinicians.¹ These tools are characterized in the literature as electronic systems that synthesize clinical knowledge, patient data, and other relevant health information to aid in complex decision-making processes. They offer patient-specific evaluations and recommendations and empower clinicians to integrate this data with their professional expertise at the point of care, facilitating more informed healthcare decisions.¹⁻⁵

The EU-oncDST concept, outlined in Deliverable D10.1⁶, offers a comprehensive, modular, transparent, interoperable, and ever-growing framework designed to centralize patient data, enhance decision-making in oncology, and improve collaboration among stakeholders.⁶ This comprehensive system includes interconnected modules for patient data management, bioinformatics for variant interpretation, clinical recommendations, molecular tumour boards (MTBs), and interoperability (Figure 1). Its primary goals are to provide personalized treatment recommendations, streamline clinical trial enrolment, support MTB decision-making, and enable seamless data exchange across institutions. The concept and its recommendations were developed through an extensive mapping exercise involving diverse stakeholders from both private and public sectors.

Figure 1: EU-oncDST concept framework developed as per in D10.1

Key strengths identified include the availability of various oncDST solutions, with bioinformatics modules for variant interpretation particularly advanced. MTB decisions consistently incorporate oncDST recommendations when available. Effective implementation holds the potential to create a learning cancer system, advancing cancer diagnosis and treatment while improving patient outcomes.

Deliverable 10.2 – EU-oncDST Capacity Building Protocol - Version 01

Currently, oncDSTs are poorly implemented in clinical care and despite their potential, several challenges need to be addressed to achieve widespread adoption of oncDST across the EU. Workflow integration requires improvement, including ensuring access to complete and comprehensive data, and automated data transfer enhancing interoperability and connectivity across systems. Standardization and harmonization in clinical implementation are critical to reduce disparities in treatment recommendations.

There is an urgent need for enhanced support in MTB discussions and reporting, including the adoption of a common language and standardized data formats. Clear guidelines are essential for defining software features, AI and manual curation processes, as well as database maintenance and updates. Furthermore, navigating complex regulatory frameworks, such as GDPR, MDR, IVDR, and emerging AI legislation, is vital to ensure compliance while fostering innovation.

Building on the conceptual framework and recommendations outlined in D10.1, this deliverable D10.2 aims to lay the groundwork for implementing these recommendations. It focuses on proposing initial actions, integrating lessons learned from previous DST implementations, suggesting elements for deeper exploration and investigation, recommending pilot use case applications, and presenting options for deployment opportunities.

Methodology

Building on the work completed previously and the recommendations outlined in D10.1 (EU-oncDST concept)⁶, CAN.HEAL consultations were organized to collaboratively define the action plan for deployment, identify pilot use case applications and consider various financial instruments. To complement the brainstorming sessions, desk research was conducted.

The overall vision

It is important to highlight that the EU-oncDST concept does not aim to develop a new tool for bioinformatics or clinical recommendations. Rather, it proposes a digital framework to enable their implementation and interoperability to support the management of the oncological process and address gaps in existing oncDSTs. This framework is designed to facilitate MTB operations at multiple levels, including institutional, national, and European. While the deployment of the EU-oncDST concept is an ambitious and time-intensive endeavour, each step taken in the field should ultimately contribute to promoting this overarching framework.

The EU-oncDST concept has been refined based on recent discussions and findings (Figure 2). A key addition is the inclusion of a patient consultation module, which will enhance patient engagement and support discussions throughout their care journey. Additionally, the interoperability module has been renamed Data-Driven Precision Oncology, as "interoperability" was considered too broad. This updated module will integrate various components, including the follow-up module, learning cancer systems (previously called "previous case database"), and digital twins also new in this updated framework.

Figure 2 EU-OncDST concept updated framework vision

Lessons learned from previous DSTs implementation

The deployment of the OncDST concept and its modules should leverage insights from previous implementations to overcome adoption barriers:

- OncDSTs may be seen as increasing clinicians' workload, especially when they disrupt established workflows, leading to resistance from providers already managing heavy oncology caseloads ^{7,8}.
- Clinicians may regard OncDSTs as a "black box," raising concerns about missed diagnoses or threats to their professional autonomy. ^{7,8} Ensuring seamless integration into existing workflows is essential to facilitate adoption. ⁹ Transparency—such as hyperlinks to supporting literature and databases—can help build trust and empower clinicians.
- Concerns about over-reliance on automated systems for complex cancer cases highlight the importance of clearly explaining how OncDST recommendations are generated and offering evidence or reasoning behind them.
- Successful adoption requires comprehensive training, intuitive user interfaces, and relevant, patient-specific recommendations, with all stakeholders involved throughout the implementation process.

Action plans

The deployment of the EU-oncDST concept should be intimately linked to the development of MTBs. There is a clear synergy between these two elements, as they are inherently interconnected and must operate in tandem to maximize their effectiveness. Implementing oncDSTs can significantly enhance the efficiency and accuracy of MTB discussions, while the feedback from MTBs can drive improvements in oncDST functionalities.

The CAN.HEAL. consortium recommends a phased deployment approach based on prioritized actions that focus on improving patient outcomes while advancing the implementation of the EU- oncDST concept (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Recommended phased deployment of the EU-oncDST

Short-term deployment

a. Toward widespread implementation of available oncDST

The primary objective is to support the widespread adoption of OncDSTs across Europe. Survey results conducted in collaboration with WP8 and WP9 revealed that only 15% of participants currently use oncDSTs dedicated to bioinformatics and clinical recommendation modules. While MTB implementation is steadily advancing throughout Europe, adopting oncDSTs—specifically bioinformatics modules and clinical recommendation tools, such as the 13 solutions included in the D10.1 mapping exercise⁶—remains limited.

To facilitate the broader implementation of OncDSTs across Europe, it will be essential to simultaneously address the challenges institutions face in effectively integrating these tools into clinical workflows and demonstrate the added value of these tools within the MTB workflow. As a starting point, the mapping exercise identified several barriers, including manual and labour-intensive data entry, incomplete data integration, the cost and reliability of tools, and the lack of locally relevant outputs and reimbursement framework.

Therefore, a pilot application should be addressed and focused on validating the use of oncDSTs within the MTB workflow. This pilot would involve representative institutions implementing oncDSTs in real-world MTB settings, testing their usability, assessing their compatibility with existing clinical workflows, and measuring their impact on decision-making processes and patient outcomes. In addition, this pilot should align with the MTB guidelines published by WP8 (D8.3) and incorporate oncDSTs' best practices, as MTBs and oncDSTs are inherently interconnected and must operate in

tandem. This approach will help demonstrate the added value oncDSTs bring to MTB discussions while identifying the key bottlenecks that impede their smooth adoption.

b. Integrate Patient-Centred consultations

The use of oncDST could bring uncertainty and unreliability to the patients in their received care. Patient consultations could offer significant benefits by improving patients' understanding of aspects such as their genetic mutations, treatment options, and the reasoning behind clinical decisions. It empowers patients to actively participate in their care, set realistic expectations for treatment outcomes, and consider clinical trials aligned with their molecular profiles. Additionally, consultations can clarify the MTB's role and the reasons for the patient's referral to the MTB. Finally, they can support informed consent for data sharing, contributing to the Data-Driven Precision Oncology module. Integrating these consultations into MTB workflows should be envisioned as a critical step toward more patient-centred cancer care. There is substantial overlap between the intended aims and applications of oncDST patient-centred consultations and established genetic counselling practices, indicating that coordination and harmonization with genetic counselling may help particularly efficiently facilitate short-term oncDST deployment.

This gap was identified in the mapping exercise, but further investigation is required to determine the best approaches for conducting these consultations. Currently, the Cancer Genome Interpreter initiative¹⁰ (CGI-Clinics) is addressing the development of an informative tool- app, the EduCGI¹¹ to increase patient knowledge and support their conversation with the clinician. This type of development requires collaborative efforts involving professionals in the field and patient representatives.

c. OncDSTs enhancement

The mapping exercise focused on the currently available solutions primarily addressing the bioinformatics and clinical recommendation modules that built the patient case for MTB discussions. These solutions presented advanced maturity although some limitations were still identified that need to be addressed. For instance:

- **A unified approach to variant annotation and interpretation across oncDSTs** by harmonizing gene transcript usage, standardizing variant classification, aligning tiering criteria and creating objective guidelines for evaluating complex biomarkers and variant combinations. Several studies have analysed oncDST performance highlighting the need for harmonized annotation, interpretation, and treatment-matching algorithms before clinical implementation¹²⁻¹⁴. Inconsistencies arise from variations in filter settings, advanced machine learning software and subjective interpretation of guidelines, which can influence patients' treatment regimen and subsequently patient outcomes. The CAN.HEAL consortium aligns with these findings and emphasizes the importance of improving clinical implementation to ensure consistent and equitable clinical decisions.
- **Develop systems that automatically match patients to clinical trials** using patient and genomic data. The large volume of patient sequencing data and complex clinical trial

eligibility criteria make it difficult, resource-intensive, and time-consuming to match patients with appropriate trials. To address this challenge, the MatchMiner initiative ¹⁵ from the Dana-Farber Cancer Institute (DFCI) offers an open-source platform that computationally matches genomically profiled cancer patients to suitable clinical trials. Similarly, the EOsc4Cancer initiative, a European-wide effort to accelerate data-driven cancer research, has launched the MTBP solution. This initiative aims to improve interoperability between clinical trial databases and clinical decision support tools (DST). Integrated with MTBP, TrialMatchAI ¹⁶ automates the process of matching patient profiles to clinical trials, focusing on genomic biomarkers and other relevant data to provide personalized trial recommendations.

- Reliability of the provided input data for the generation of clinical annotations and recommendations by the tool. Limitations have been identified for paediatric patients and for haematological cancers e.g. multiple myeloma. Pilot applications focusing on collecting data for specific populations or cancer subtypes should be considered.
- Reporting variants of uncertain significance (VUS) within the case-building report for MTB discussions. This approach is exemplified by the BoostDM method, which supports the comprehensive analysis of single nucleotide variants in cancer-related genes. BoostDM uses an advanced machine-learning approach to classify variants, including VUS, as either drivers or passengers in tumorigenesis. It predicts the functional impact of these variants on protein structure and their potential role in oncogenesis. By evaluating mutational features—such as mutation type (e.g., missense, nonsense, splice site), location, and data from large tumour sample datasets—BoostDM provides more accurate variant classifications compared to rule-based methods. Additionally, it assigns scores to indicate the likelihood of a variant being a driver mutation, offering valuable insights into its potential role in cancer.^{17,18}
- Lack of advanced learning software integration in the diagnosis module to improve diagnostic recommendations such as for cancer of unknown primary (CUP). One example that addresses this challenge is the initiative led by Institut Curie (France), which has implemented a national MTB and developed the TransCUPtomics AI tool. This tool utilizes technologies to analyze tumour transcriptomic data, aiding in the identification of the tissue of origin. This AI-driven approach facilitates the development of personalized treatment strategies for CUP patients.^{19,20}

Mid-term deployment

d. Supporting MTB deployment through widespread MTB module adoption and implementation

The MTB module is becoming central and essential in supporting uniform, reliable, and transparent MTB discussions and recommendations. As the deployment of MTBs continues, it is important to recognize that the MTB module is still in its nascent stages and must evolve alongside these ongoing deployment efforts. Unlike the other oncDSTs modules, the MTB module is still addressing critical operational needs and ensuring interoperability with existing systems.

Currently, D10.1⁶ identified solutions developed through national and European initiatives such as:

- BALLETT app (Jessa hospital_V1) developed by the CAN.HEAL partner for the BALLETT study²¹
- Cancer Genome Interpreter¹⁰ (CGI-Clinics_v2)
- cBioPortal adapted^{22–25} for MTB use by the MIRACUM MII consortium (cBioPortal adapted_v6)
- MTB portal²⁶ (MTBP - Karolinska Institutet).

Promoting sustainability and widespread adoption of these platforms will facilitate the establishment of both national and European MTBs, allowing for instance countries to upload patient cases for expert opinions through these tools or help reduce care discrepancies, particularly in regions where implementing institutional or national MTBs is challenging.

To ensure the continued progress of the MTB module, key enhancements should include clear patient case visualizations, incorporation of alternative testing results, an agnostic approach to data integration, and a link to data-driven precision oncology modules and automated clinical trial matching systems. The platform should also accommodate national contexts and facilitate structured MTB report creation. As the core of the EU-oncDST concept, its implementation must align with the overarching framework and workflow, ensuring interoperability and adaptability to meet the diverse users' needs.

Further development opportunities for MTB modules include collaboration with the Electronic Health Data Space (EHDS) ²⁷ and the Joint Action (JA) EUnetCCC ²⁸ which could further strengthen its impact and effectiveness across Europe.

e. Impact assessment of EU-oncDST implementation

Implementing the EU-oncDST concept will require substantial resources, including financial investment, enhanced infrastructure, and specialized personnel. This involves staffing for MTB patient consultation services to help patients understand their genetic mutations, treatment options, and the rationale behind clinical decisions. Additionally, personnel will be needed for internal technical digital support, ensuring the seamless integration of the EU-oncDST digital framework within the MTB workflow and also assisting clinicians and MTB coordinators in effectively utilising the tools. Furthermore, achieving the desired interoperability across all aspects of the concept will demand substantial investment in database maintenance, cybersecurity, quality assurance, scalability, access control, and data monitoring. While these requirements represent a considerable effort, they are expected to deliver long-term benefits, including reduced costs through optimized treatment and diagnostic processes, as well as enhanced workforce productivity.

To address these considerations, we recommend creating a comprehensive roadmap to assess the impacts of implementing the EU-oncDST concept across Europe. This roadmap should encompass an analysis of its effects on the workforce, its impact on existing infrastructure, and a thorough health technology assessment (HTA). This effort should be undertaken in coordination with

initiatives such as EUNetCCC, JA-PCM, UNCAN²⁹, and EHDS to ensure alignment and enhance overall effectiveness.

f. Streamlining regulations, guidelines, and reimbursement frameworks

The implementation of the EU-oncDST concept will present complex regulatory challenges, as the various modules will need to comply with GDPR, IVDR, MDR, and the AI Act, often simultaneously. To navigate these challenges, it is essential to streamline certification pathways and accreditation processes for these modules, ensuring compliance with all relevant legal and regulatory frameworks for optimal safety, privacy, and ethical standards. Additionally, the establishment of a reimbursement framework is critical for the financial sustainability and broad accessibility of oncDST tools. This will require close collaboration with healthcare payers and national reimbursement agencies to create clear criteria and standardized processes for coverage and compensation. This effort will be initiated based on the data and evidence gathered from the short-term deployment, ensuring that the reimbursement framework aligns with real-world usage and impact. To address in deep these regulatory challenges, the approach of implementing an actively developed regulatory sandbox could provide a potential solution. A regulatory sandbox is a controlled environment where new technologies, such as oncDST tools, can be tested and validated under regulatory supervision without the immediate need to comply with all standard regulatory requirements. This approach allows for flexibility in testing innovative solutions while ensuring that safety and compliance are maintained, ultimately providing a foundation for broader regulatory approval.³⁰

To ensure secure handling in compliance with legal requirements, it is necessary to develop guidelines for defining the legal framework surrounding data storage, retention and disposal. Similarly, establishing protocols for timely and consistent database updates is vital to provide clinicians with the most current and accurate information, to reduce discrepancies between various used systems. Achieving this will require collaboration among database curators, bioinformatics experts, and clinicians, as well as conducting regular evaluations to maintain data consistency and accuracy.

Long-term deployment

g. Harmonized short- and mid-term activities

The development activities should remain focused on the ultimate goal of creating the digital framework proposed by the EU-oncDST concept. Short- and mid-term activities should be integrated and aligned throughout the development process to ensure they support the achievement of this overarching objective.

h. Leverage the data-driven precision oncology module

The advanced machine learning system in the data-driven precision oncology module will primarily rely on MTB structured reports within the learning cancer system and the follow-up module to track patient progress and treatment responses. The information retrieved by AI should be accessible through query access on the MTB platform, providing insights and support during MTB discussions to review the course of treatment and outcomes for specific cases by MTB members. It is essential to consider this development not only at an institutional level but also at national and European

levels. The integration of such advanced technology has the potential to be a game-changer in the field. However, this will raise the challenge of the cross-border data-sharing agreement.

Various ongoing and upcoming initiatives, such as EOSC4cancer³¹, 1+genome³², CGI-Clinics, MTBP, JA PCM, JA EUNetCCC, and others, are centralizing efforts to pave the way for this approach.

i. Digital Twin exploration to support MTB recommendations

Exploring how digital twins can be incorporated to support MTB discussions should be a key consideration. Digital twins hold significant promise by dynamically reflecting various data sources, including electronic health records (EHR), -omics data, physical indicators, demographic information, and lifestyle factors. As they continuously adapt to real-time data, digital twins are expected to predict future scenarios and provide valuable insights for MTBs, enhancing diagnostics, prognosis, and treatment recommendations. Additionally, this system will empower patients by providing access to their digital twin data, including personalized health insights, treatment plans, and progress tracking, allowing them to take a more active role in managing their health and facilitating engagement with healthcare providers.³³

The European Union is advancing virtual human twins (VHTs) through its European VHT Initiative³⁴, which aims to enhance health and care solutions. Two prominent projects are EDITH (European Digital Twin for Healthcare)³⁵, focused on creating a roadmap for integrated VHTs, and DIGITALEU³⁶, which is developing a cutting-edge digital platform for VHT model integration and validation.

Deployment opportunities

To achieve the goals mentioned above, certain activities will need to be addressed in ongoing and future initiatives and will need to include public-private partnerships. We have identified initiatives and key instruments that could effectively support the development, commercialization, and scaling of innovative solutions. These instruments are designed to bridge the gap between research and practical application, particularly in high-cost and high-risk domains such as healthcare technology, medical devices, and biotechnology.

- **National initiatives:** in several countries or regions, national precision oncology initiatives are initiated and ongoing. A list is available in WP8 deliverable D8.2 Genomic national initiatives (CAN.HEAL). Further deployment should build on these initiatives in alignment with the here proposed action plan.
- **Ongoing and upcoming international initiatives:** Further deployment should build on the results and activities of current initiatives in alignment with the here proposed action plan.

Horizon Europe initiatives:

- EOSC4Cancer: use case on CDSS tools³¹
- UNCAN: activities on data standardisation²⁹
- 1 million genome: standardized data collection and facilitate harmonized analyses across different research settings^{37,38}

EU4Health Programme initiatives:

- PCM4EU (Personalized Cancer Medicine for all EU citizens): activities on Clinical Decision Support Systems (CDSS) tools for clinical decision-making in oncology³⁹
- EUNetCCC: activities on data standardisation and CDSS²⁸
- EHDS: activities on data (common standards, infrastructures, governance)²⁷
- JANE-2: activities focused on developing networks of expertise (NoEs), including but not limited to omics technologies⁴⁰
- JA PCM (start Oct 2025): activities on MTB, data standards and data-sharing platforms.

 • **Other instruments:**

- **The European Partnership for Personalised Medicine (EP PerMed):** is a new platform launched to promote and advance personalized medicine in Europe.^{41,42} This partnership combines funding from the European Commission, national, and regional sources to improve future healthcare through personalized therapy, diagnosis, and prevention.⁴¹
- The Horizon Europe (EU Research & Innovation) programme for 2021-2027 includes a comprehensive set of grant instruments defined by the European Commission to support a wide range of research and innovation activities. These instruments are strategically designed to fund various stages of research and innovation, from fundamental scientific exploration to market-ready technological solutions. The grant mechanisms encompass different funding approaches, with each instrument tailored to specific research objectives, technological readiness levels, and potential impact. This ensures a flexible and comprehensive approach to supporting the European research ecosystem across various domains and stages of technological maturity. Among these instruments are the Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP) action and Public Procurement of Innovative Solutions (PPI), which are explained below.⁴³⁻⁴⁵
- **Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP)** is a strategic approach used by the public sector to procure research and development (R&D) services. It is designed to stimulate innovation by engaging multiple suppliers to develop new solutions that meet public sector needs. PCP involves a phased approach where R&D is purchased from several competing suppliers to compare different solution approaches. This process includes stages such as solution design, prototyping, and testing of limited product volumes. The goal is to de-risk the development of innovative solutions and prepare them for potential commercialization through Public Procurement of Innovative Solutions (PPI).⁴⁶⁻⁴⁹
- **Public Procurement of Innovative Solutions (PPI)** occurs when the public sector acts as an early adopter for innovative products or services that are close to market readiness but not yet available on a large scale. Unlike PCP, PPI does not involve R&D but focuses on scaling up production and integrating new solutions into existing systems. PPI helps trigger industry investment by creating a demand for innovative solutions that meet specific quality and price criteria. This approach enables the public sector to procure cutting-edge technologies while fostering market growth and competition.^{47,49}

- **Innovative Health Initiative (IHI)** is a public-private partnership aimed at advancing health research and innovation in Europe. It focuses on developing new healthcare solutions, improving patient outcomes, and fostering collaboration between various stakeholders, including industry, academia, and patient organizations. The IHI aims to address complex health challenges by pooling resources and expertise in the pre-competitive area to drive innovation in the healthcare sector.⁵⁰ We could focus on key topics such as standardizing annotation and interpretation, data sharing and the enrichment of databases through pilot applications, and supporting open market consultations for pre-commercial procurement all with the aim of developing the overall EU-oncDST digital framework.

In annexe, an overview is given in Table 1 (provided by AquAS, CAN.HEAL WP3 partner) to help stakeholders better understand and evaluate some of the tools available within various European innovation programs, specifically focusing on Horizon Europe (EU research and innovation), PCP, and IHI. The table describes each program, highlighting their respective advantages and disadvantages, offering a clear comparison between the different options and in this way offering support in the choice of the most suitable instrument for the specific project.

Conclusion

The EU-oncDST concept represents a significant leap forward in oncology decision support, offering a comprehensive digital framework for MTB decision-making. This approach enhances the implementation and interoperability of available oncDSTs, centralizes patient data, fosters collaboration among stakeholders, and promotes innovation. The CAN.HEAL consortium's proposed strategy emphasizes a symbiotic relationship between MTB deployment and oncDST implementation, particularly in the short term, where challenges like data entry and tool reliability are addressed alongside their incorporation into MTB workflows. A pilot application in real-world MTB settings, aligned with MTB guidelines, will validate the added value of available oncDSTs in enhancing discussions and, by extension, their impact on patient outcomes. Moreover, feedback from MTBs will further refine oncDST functionality, fostering continuous improvement. The development of MTB modules and the integration of technologies like AI and digital twins will also contribute to building a learning cancer system and advancing cancer diagnosis, treatment, and patient outcomes.

Successful implementation of the EU-oncDST concept will require significant resources, including financial investment, infrastructure enhancement, and specialized personnel. Despite these challenges, the long-term benefits are clear—optimized treatment processes, reduced costs, and improved workforce productivity will help drive the transformation of precision oncology into a robust, equitable, and sustainable healthcare model. By leveraging national and EU initiatives, the EU-oncDST concept has the potential to evolve into a cornerstone of precision oncology, enhancing MTB discussions and driving continuous learning in cancer treatment. Ultimately, its successful implementation will lay the foundation for a more integrated, data-driven, and patient-centric cancer care approach.

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Deliverable 10.2 – EU-oncDST Capacity Building Protocol - Version 01

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Deliverable 10.2 – EU-oncDST Capacity Building Protocol - Version 01

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Deliverable 10.2 – EU-oncDST Capacity Building Protocol - Version 01

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Annexe

Table 1: Comparison of EU Innovation Initiatives: Support Provided by European Research and Innovation Programs

	Horizon Europe (EU research & innovation)	Pre-commercial procurement (PCP)	Innovative Health Initiative (IHI)
Description	<p>Grant instrument defined by the financing entity (European Commission).</p> <p><u>Horizon Europe</u> is the ambitious EU research & innovation framework programme for 2021-2027 with a budget of 95,5 billion.</p> <p>Its overarching goals are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -to strengthen the EU's scientific and technological bases and the European Research Area (ERA); -to boost Europe's innovation capacity, competitiveness and jobs; -to deliver on citizen's priorities and sustain our socio-economic model and values. <p>...with a particular focus on creating impact or the European Green Deal, the digital and sustainability transition and recovery from the coronavirus crisis.</p> <p>HE structures: Horizon Europe is divided into 3 Pillars:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pillar 1) Excellence Science (Frontier research projects defined/driven by top researchers, postdoctoral fellowships, funding and doctoral training networks, Marie-Curie Actions and research infrastructures' research), • Pillar 2) Global Challenges & European Industrial Competitiveness. Support research for societal challenges and reinforce technological and industrial capacities through Clusters (6) that are financed by RIA, IA and CSA actions: i)Health; ii)Culture, iii)Creativity and Inclusive Society; iv)Civil Security for Society; v)Digital, Industry and Space; v) Climate, Energy & Mobility; vi)Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture & Environment) and the Joint Research Centre which supports EU/National policymakers with independent scientific evidence and technical support. • Pillar 3) Innovative Europe to make Europe a frontrunner in market-creating innovation via the European Innovation Council. It also helps to develop the European innovation landscape through the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) based on the knowledge 	<p>Demand-driven instrument.</p> <p><u>Pre-Commercial Procurement (PCP)</u> can be used when there are no near-to-the-market solutions yet and new research and development are needed. PCP can then compare the pros and cons of alternative competing solutions approaches. PCP de-risks investment by breaking the research and development into competitive phases: solution design, prototyping, development and first product testing.</p> <p>At the EU level, grant instruments can be used to co-fund Pre-commercial Procurement (PCP) (Horizon Europe).</p> <p>In general, this instrument is used to address unmet needs that need a long-term strategy. Buyers will need to plan their investment across a few years before seeing the actual impact.</p> <p>Reference:</p> <p>European Commission, Pre-Commercial Procurement https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/support-policy-making/shaping-eu-research-and-innovation-policy/new-european-innovation-agenda/innovation-procurement/pre-commercial-procurement_en</p> <p><u>When proposals are submitted and when Call for Tender are launched:</u></p> <p><u>Buyers' business case needs to be clear</u></p>	<p>Public-private partnership: Grant instrument defined by the financing entities (EC and the main industry associations).</p> <p><u>IHI</u> is designed to build on what worked well in IMI (Innovative Medicines Initiative), address the lessons learnt, and leverage the benefits of cross-sectoral collaboration in research and innovation to better respond to current and emerging health needs.</p> <p>IHI works by running open, competitive calls for proposals, and we continue to publish draft topic texts before the call launch to give applicants additional time to work on their proposals.</p> <p>As in IMI, IHI brings together diverse stakeholders (universities, companies large and small, and other health stakeholders) in collaborative projects that address disease areas where there is a high burden on patients and/or society.</p> <p>Who Can Apply for IHI Funding? IHI funding is open to a wide range of entities, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Academic and Research Institutions: Universities, research centres, and academic consortia. •Industry Partners: Both large companies and SMEs working in healthcare, biotech, pharmaceuticals, or related fields. •Patient Organizations: Groups representing patient needs and perspectives. •Healthcare Providers and Public Health Entities: Organizations focused on delivering care or improving public health systems. <p>Reference: https://www.ih.europa.eu/apply-funding https://www.ih.europa.eu/apply-funding/why-apply</p> <p>In short, IHI has two main differentiated phases:</p> <p>Phase 1 (call development): Focus on clarifying that this phase is about defining funding priorities and calls rather than project selection. Participants: European Commission, Private entities from main industry associations (COCIR, EFPIA (including Vaccines Europe), EuropaBio, and MedTech Europe), and IHI Executive Director and Program Office</p>

	<p>triangle (education, research & innovation). The part Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area (ERA), as a transversal action, increases support for EU MMSS for their national research and innovation potential.</p> <p>Finally, Horizon Europe will be implemented also through the European Defence Fund and complemented by the Euratom Research and Training Programme.</p> <p>EU missions (5) are commitments to solve some of the greatest challenges facing our world like fighting cancer, adapting to climate change, protecting our oceans, living in greener cities and ensuring soil health and food. Each mission operates as: <i>research projects, policy measures or even legislative initiatives to achieve a measurable goal.</i> EU missions will contribute to the goals of the <i>European Green Deal, Europe's Beating Cancer Plan</i> as well as the <i>Sustainable Development Goals</i>.</p> <p>European Partnerships bring the Commission and private and/or public partners together to address some of Europe's most pressing challenges through concerted research and innovation initiatives. They are a key implementation tool of Horizon Europe and contribute significantly to achieving the EU's political priorities. There are 3 types: European Co-programme Partnerships, European Co-funded Partnerships and European Institutionalised Partnerships.</p> <p>Funding: HE budget is around 95,5 billion for 2021-2027 including 5,4 billion from Next Generation EU (recovery and resilience for the future) and 4,6 billion for additional reinforcement.</p> <p>Participation in Horizon Europe: It will be restricted according to the necessities and requirements of each Pillar and calls to: cooperation between legal entities established in Member States only, Member States and Associated Countries, and/or certain third countries Participating Countries or International cooperation</p> <p>Who can apply: Research organisations, Policy Makers, Citizens, Non-Governmental Organizations and Industry.</p> <p>Type of call: Pillar 1. Excellence Science: (bottom-up); Pillar 2. Global Challenges & EU Industrial Competition: (Top-Down), Pillar 3. Innovative Europe: Bottom-up)</p> <p>What is your approach: Research progress, Innovation, Business Development of Mission</p>		<p>Phase 2 (proposal evaluation): Emphasize the role of independent external experts in the grant review process, as they are critical to ensuring objectivity.</p> <p>Both phases could include the explicit role of aligning calls and projects with IHI's cross-sectoral and collaborative focus, as this is a key distinguishing feature of IHI. Participants: External evaluation committee, private and public sector representative, IHI Executive Director and Program Office</p> <p>The initiative emphasizes pre-competitive research, aiming to lay the groundwork for future health innovations without directly delivering products or services to the market or healthcare systems. The work supported by IHI should be pre-competitive, meaning it will not deliver products or services directly into healthcare systems or the market. There are no specific requirements regarding TRL. IP rules in IHI projects are defined under the Horizon Europe General Model Grant Agreement (article 16 and Annex 5). TRL Flexibility: <i>There are no explicit TRL thresholds that projects must meet. The emphasis is on advancing scientific understanding and technological development without the immediate goal of market introduction.</i></p> <p>IHI primarily targets projects in mid-stage research and development, where technologies are being validated, tested, and demonstrated in relevant environments.</p> <p>Diversity of IHI projects: Joining an IHI project allows participants to contribute to high-quality research aimed at making a tangible impact on patients and health systems.</p> <p>- Involvement in IHI projects offers organizations, access to the entire value chain of health research and innovation. This can lead to the development and enhancement of technologies, products, and services</p> <p><u>When Calls are launched and when proposals are submitted: Contributing partners' business model needs to be clear</u></p>
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<p>What kind of impact do you expect to achieve: Scientific (Pillar 1), Societal (Pillar 2), Economic (Pillar 3)</p> <p>What about EU funding: For Additional resources to achieve your objectives; access to new partners, access to the SoA knowledge, circulation of ideas and cross-fertilisation</p> <p>What are the TRL pathways: TRL1-TRL3: Pillar 1; TRL4-TRL6: Pillar 2; TRL6-TRL9: Pillar 3</p> <p>- Relevant aspects are taken into consideration: Cross-cutting issues such as Gender Equality, Ethics & Research Integrity and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) have great importance in all funded projects.</p> <p>- Technology & market expectations are deeply monitored: The Technology Readiness Level (TRLs) pathway is well defined according to the three Pillars of expectations (idea to the market). The same for the Market Readiness Levels (MRLs) pathways (idea to scalable business)</p> <p>References: -EU Funding & Tender Portal: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/programmes/horizon -HE Programme-guide horizon-en.pdf. HE Programme Guide: v4.1-01.05.2024 - Horizon Europe Work Programme 2023-2025. General Introduction.</p> <p>When proposals are submitted:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · <u>future adopters’ business case is unclear</u> · <u>Industrial partners’ business model is unclear</u> 		
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Advantages	<p>❶ EC funding: For Additional resources to achieve your objectives; access to new partners, access to the SoA knowledge, circulation of ideas and cross-fertilisation</p> <p>❷ It is a well-structured program addressed to current EU problems among others: It is split into 3 Pillars very well defined (Scientific, societal challenges & Industry reinforcement and innovation). A Strategic Plan and expected impacts are also contemplated to better identify proposals' requirements (<i>social, economic, ecological and scientific aspirations</i>) based on Policy Priorities. A wide call offers (bottom-up or top-down) the most suitable to fit your project or problem to be tackled.</p> <p>❸ Interesting funding for public and private entities especially for SMEs and start-ups.</p> <p>❹ EC support: Horizon Europe contemplates mechanisms, documentation, National Contact Point(NCP), Online Manual and the EC web (<i>Gender and Funding Portal</i>) to help individuals and Consortia with the preparation & submission of proposals as well as during funded projects' development. Once the project is funded, also a Project Officer (EC) will be assigned to the project to guide coordinators to comply with HE rules, and project commitments and solve any incident that occurs during project time.</p> <p>❺ EU Networking: High opportunity to take part in a European Network after belonging to a Consortia.</p> <p>❻ Promote reputation: Projects supported under Horizon Europe have a track record of publishing research in prominent journals and presenting at international conferences, etc.</p>	<p>❶ EC funding programmes available (depending on the programmes and the calls)</p> <p>❷ Aims at improving the quality and/or efficiency of public services: PCP enables the development of innovative healthcare solutions that can enhance service delivery and efficiency.</p> <p>❸ Allows obtaining better quality products at competitive prices: By involving multiple suppliers in the R&D phase, PCP fosters competition, which can result in higher-quality products at more competitive prices aligned with buyers' business cases.</p> <p>❹ Reduces risk of failure in follow-up PPI procurements: PCP helps refine products through phased development and testing, minimizing the risk of failure in subsequent Public Procurement of Innovative (PPI) projects.</p> <p>❺ In the case of cross-border PCPs/Groups of buyers: Knowledge sharing among groups of buyers with the same unmet needs promotes standard solutions.</p> <p>❻ Better use of public resources: PCP ensures that public funds are invested in targeted R&D activities that address specific healthcare needs, leading to more efficient use of resources.</p> <p>❼ Creates high-added-value jobs in Europe and contributes to sustainable economic growth: PCP promotes job creation in high-tech sectors and supports the growth of SMEs and start-ups, contributing to a more sustainable economy.</p> <p>❽ Mitigation of the risk of unmeeting the expectation: The PCP is a demand-driven instrument and all the requirements and needs are expected to take into consideration the expectations of all the impacted stakeholders. Representatives from all the impacted stakeholders are expected to be part of the team that evaluates the offers and monitors the contract.</p> <p>❾ Accelerates the process of bringing scientific results to market: PCP bridges the gap between research and market-ready products, speeding up the commercialization of new technologies.</p> <p>❿ Shortens time-to-market for innovative products and services: The structured phases of PCP allow for faster iteration and development, reducing the time required to bring innovations to market.</p> <p>❶❶ Facilitates the access of new innovative players to the market: PCP lowers entry barriers for SMEs and start-ups,</p>	<p>❶ Access to Funding: Organizations established in the EU or countries associated with Horizon Europe are eligible for IHI funding. This primarily supports entities like universities, research organizations, patient groups, SMEs, and mid-sized companies. <i>"Participation in IHI not only supports early-stage research but can also position organizations to secure follow-up funding or licensing deals for their innovations."</i></p> <p>❷ Alignment with EU Health Priorities: IHI projects are designed to address key public health needs, ensuring that funded initiatives are in line with the European Union's health priorities. <i>"IHI funding helps align research outputs with market readiness and regulatory requirements, reducing the gap between research and commercial adoption."</i></p> <p>❸ Networking Opportunities: IHI projects unite top teams from industry, academia, SMEs, patient groups, and other health-related sectors. <i>"Collaborations fostered within IHI projects can lead to strategic alliances, licensing opportunities, or early adoption by healthcare systems, providing market access for innovative solutions."</i> Cross-sector collaboration: Industry involvement fosters collaboration across various sectors, integrating technologies and expertise to develop innovative health solutions. This cross-sectoral approach aims to address complex health challenges by combining pharmaceuticals, medical devices, digital tools, and more.</p> <p>❹ Open access to knowledge: participants in IHI projects engage in cutting-edge cross-sector health research and innovation, gaining early access to project results. The open sharing of knowledge and data within projects can provide access to resources like biobanks, laboratories, clinical centres, and databases. <i>"Open access to knowledge can fast-track innovation and provide participants with competitive insights for commercial development."</i></p> <p>❺ Promote reputation: Projects supported under IMI have a track record of publishing research in prominent journals and presenting at international conferences, etc.</p> <p>❻ Enhance competitiveness and innovation: By engaging in IHI projects, industry partners aim to boost the global competitiveness of Europe's health industries. Collaborative projects are designed to deliver safe, effective health innovations covering the entire spectrum of care—from prevention to diagnosis and treatment—particularly in areas with unmet public health needs.</p> <p>❼ The IHI is a public-private partnership among the EC, the MedTech and Pharma industry. The contributing partners for each of the calls are transparently known from the very beginning All the players from the MedTech and Pharma industries have the same opportunity to</p>
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		<p>enabling them to compete and succeed in the healthcare market.</p> <p>1 2 Stimulates company growth and attracts private investment: Success in PCP can enhance a company's profile, attracting further investment and supporting business expansion.</p> <p>1 3 Market is known: Buyers can be future adopters/implementers of your solution.</p> <p>1 4 IP Management: IPRs are regulated in the procedures and the contractors can exploit their knowledge and IPRs.</p>	<p>contribute to the IHI calls. The consortium agreement in play is designed in a way the IPRs regulations are clear from the very beginning. Any collaboration from any public entity in any IHI call can favour big companies able to pay the fee to their association and act as a contributing partner.</p> <p><i>"Effective IP management within IHI consortia ensures that participants retain value from their innovations, enabling licensing or exclusive rights for commercialization."</i></p>
<p>Disadvantages</p>	<p>1 Scaling-up: In most of the cases, it is difficult to scale up beyond Horizon funding actions (mandatory).</p> <p>2 Horizon Europe is a big and complex structure. It is recommended to have a highly talented Project Manager structure at the entity for proposal preparation & submission, negotiation and monitoring steps (after EC funding).</p> <p>3 Strict compliance with the EC projects' rules during all the process of submission or project development in terms of financial aspects, equity, security,... For instance, strict audits in European projects are critical tools for ensuring integrity, transparency, and effectiveness in the use of EU funds and ensuring that funded projects deliver the expected value. As a result, much time is dedicated to good compliance rules.</p> <p>4 Financial aspects such as the <i>Average person/month differences</i> in Europe could create inequalities in some partners' budgets.</p> <p>- Consortium management risks due to internal changes in entities, lack of management commitment, geopolitical aspects,...) resulting in additional risks during project development with non-experienced coordinators. IPR's vulnerability due to a deficient Knowledge exploitation and protection once the project ended.</p> <p>5 Market Uncertainty: Even after successful development, there is no guarantee of widespread adoption or market success. The competitive nature of PCP might leave some companies without a market-ready product or sufficient market share.</p> <p>6 IP Management Issues: Disputes over intellectual property rights can arise, especially in collaborations involving multiple stakeholders. Companies must ensure that their innovations are protected, which can be complicated in a PCP framework.</p>	<p>1 Uncertain ROI (Return on Investment) for the buyer: <i>There's no guarantee that the developed technology will achieve the expected cost savings or improvements in patient outcomes. R&D investments may not always result in a commercially viable product.</i></p> <p>2 Strict compliance with procurement directives and legal frameworks + strict compliance with the EC projects' rules during all the process of submission or project development in terms of financial aspects, equity, security,... For instance, strict audits in European projects are critical tools for ensuring integrity, transparency, and effectiveness in the use of EU funds and ensuring that funded projects deliver the expected value. As a result, much time is dedicated to good compliance rules.</p> <p>3 Risk of Budget Overruns for the contractors: R&D processes can be unpredictable, potentially leading to higher costs than initially anticipated. Managing multiple phases of PCP can strain financial resources if not carefully controlled.</p> <p>4 Delayed Benefit for the contractors: The long development timelines can delay the realization of benefits from new technologies. The contractors need to take into account the length of the process through the R+D, full concept, CE mark, evidence generation, and market access when submitting their proposal to a PCP. Still, it is not clear if the length of the overall process is larger than the one resulting from a collaborative R&D or IHI project.</p> <p>5 Regulatory Risks: New technologies might face challenges in obtaining regulatory approval, delaying their integration into healthcare systems. Non-compliance with healthcare standards and regulations can lead to additional costs or project failure. Buyers and contractors need to constantly monitor changes in</p>	<p>1 Demanding Resource Requirements (challenge): Participating in an IHI project typically involves joining a large, multi-partner consortium, which can be both rewarding and resource-intensive. Smaller organizations or research teams with limited personnel or funding may find it challenging to dedicate the necessary time, administrative resources, and coordination efforts required to meet the demands of such projects. If your team has tight resources, it's essential to assess whether you can effectively manage these commitments while still achieving your research goals.</p> <p>2 Strict compliance with the EC projects' rules during all the process of submission or project development in terms of financial aspects, equity, security,... For instance, strict audits in European projects are critical tools for ensuring integrity, transparency, and effectiveness in the use of EU funds and ensuring that funded projects deliver the expected value. As a result, much time is dedicated to good compliance rules.</p> <p>3 Market-driven initiative aligned with EC priorities: Corporations dependency affecting the results: The private sector and big corporations from the pharma sector, one of the most prominent, can promote commercial interest over public health on the results.</p> <p>4 Uncertainty in the results: Some innovative initiatives might not produce tangible and short-term results.</p> <p>5 Regulatory Risks: resulting R+D might face challenges in obtaining regulatory approval, delaying their integration into healthcare systems. Non-compliance with healthcare standards and regulations can lead to additional costs or project failure. Project partners need to constantly monitor changes in the regulations that can affect the productization of the solutions.</p> <p>6 Unmet Expectations: If the innovation fails to meet its anticipated outcomes or improve healthcare delivery, it can result in a loss of public trust, as the expectations set by the initiative remain unfulfilled.</p>

	<p>⑦ Regulatory Risks: resulting R+D might face challenges in obtaining regulatory approval, delaying their integration into healthcare systems. Non-compliance with healthcare standards and regulations can lead to additional costs or project failure. Project partners need to constantly monitor changes in the regulations that can affect the productization of the solutions.</p> <p>⑧ Unmet Expectations: If the product/service does not meet the anticipated outcomes or improve healthcare delivery, public trust could be undermined. Promised innovations may not materialize, leading to dissatisfaction and scepticism about public spending on innovation.</p>	<p>the regulations that can affect the productization of the solutions.</p> <p>⑤ In the case of EC co-funded PCP, we have risks related to the buyers' group: investment commitment and procurement commitment can change during the life of the project.</p> <p>⑥ Unmet Expectations: If the product/service does not meet the anticipated outcomes or improve healthcare delivery, public trust could be undermined. Promised innovations may not materialize, leading to dissatisfaction and scepticism about public spending on innovation.</p>	<p>Promised innovations may not materialize, leading to dissatisfaction and scepticism about public spending on innovation.</p> <p>⑦ Complexity in creating a sustainable business model on top of Open Access Knowledge</p> <p>⑧ The SME can have the same problems and disadvantages that they have in a standard R+D collaboration.</p>
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